

POLYEMBRYONY PHENOMENON IN BROAD-LEAVED MANDARIN UNSHIU AND GEORGIAN LEMON HYBRID OFFSPRING

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Introduction: *Citrus plants represent an excellent subject for studying the polyembryony phenomenon, as citrus and other orange-family plants are characterized by polyembryony - when two or more embryos develop in a single ovule.*

It has been established that more embryos develop in the seeds of a particular citrus variety (or form) than actually germinate, meaning fewer seedlings are obtained from seeds after sowing. Seedlings are particularly not obtained from embryos that have poorly developed or completely undeveloped cotyledons. It is possible that among two, three, or more seedlings obtained from a single seed, there may be two or more grafted plants (natural seedlings). The germination of two or more plants from one seed is associated with the development of additional embryos from nucellar cells. Embryos originating from nucellar cells are called nucellar embryos, while plants obtained from such embryos are called plants of nucellar origin or nucellar offspring [1,4,5,9, 14].

Keywords: *distant hybridization, polyembryony, nucellar and hybrid offspring.*

Experiment: In studying polyembryony, it is important to use offspring obtained from preliminary sowing of hybrid citrus seeds. The experiment was conducted at the Agricultural Research Center of Akaki Tsereteli State University, where the project theme "Improvement of Agricultural Characteristics of Citrus Plants and Obtaining New Forms Using Selection Methods" was implemented. As mentioned, the project's goal was to obtain new perspective forms of citrus, and for this purpose we used distant hybridization. The initial components used in crossing combinations were: Early Maturing Trifoliata and Citrus Ichangensis hybrid "Caucasus" (both new forms), Georgian lemon, and broad-leaved mandarin Unshiu.

The scientific team conducted the citrus plant crossing process according to various combinations. Specifically, to obtain nucellar offspring of hybrid nature, we pollinated flowers of Georgian lemon and broad-leaved mandarin Unshiu with pollen from Early Maturing Trifoliata and Citrus Ichangensis hybrid "Kavkasia". Hybrid seeds were sown and the resulting hybrid offspring were genetically studied from the moment of germination until the end of two growing seasons [2,3,6,7,8, 15]. Observation of the offspring was conducted from the moment of sowing, and they were systematically studied according to bio-morphological characteristics and phenological phases. It should be noted that separation of sexual hybrid offspring from nucellar offspring is possible according to external phenotypic characteristics: leaf form, pubescence and size, petiole wings, coloration of young shoots, leaf scent, and other characteristics. Although these characteristics are phenotypic, they are also genotypic (hereditary), and we compared the initial parents precisely by these characteristics [10,11,12, 16]. Because the characteristics of the cold-resistant male parent almost always dominate in distant hybrids, offspring that clearly bear the above-mentioned phenotypic characteristics of the male parent were considered sexual hybrids and separated individually, while the remainder (offspring resembling the mother), as nucellar offspring, were separated, too. The results of such study are presented in Table #1.

Table #1
Germination of Hybrid Seeds and Polyembryony

#	Combination			Including
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		Number of Seeds Sown	Number of Offspring Raised	Hybrid Offspring		Nucellar Offspring	
			Piece	Piece	%	Piece	%
1.	Tangerine broadleaf Unshiu × Early Maturing Trifoliata	100	62	48	77.4	14	22.6
2.	Tangerine broadleaf Unshiu × Citrus Ichangensis „Caucasus”	100	73	58	79.5	15	19.5
3.	Georgian lemon × Early Maturing Trifoliata	120	90	68	75.6	22	24.4
4.	Georgian lemon × Citrus Ichangensis „Caucasus”	120	94	83	88.2	11	11.8

From the materials presented in the table, it is clearly evident that the possibilities of obtaining nucellar offspring during distant hybridization in citrus are generally low and vary according to crossing combinations.

When analyzing the obtained material, one general pattern is noticeable: although there is no significant difference between them, the germination capacity of hybrid seeds is still relatively higher with Citrus Ichangensis in both combinations than with Early Maturing Trifoliata, which may be due to the relatively higher viability of Citrus Ichangensis pollen grains - their higher fertilization capacity.

Results: The research established that the possibility of obtaining nucellar offspring in the combination of broad-leaved mandarin Unshiu and Early Maturing Trifoliata is higher than in other combinations. Although the percentage difference in obtaining nucellar offspring between combinations is not large, its confirmation is necessary because the very possibility of obtaining nucellar offspring is limited and appears to be determined by varietal biological characteristics.

Based on the research results, during distant hybridization with Citrus Ichangensis, greater possibilities were found for obtaining nucellar offspring of hybrid nature; plants of this group are highly significant for breeding purposes, as the possibility is created that along with cold resistance obtained from the male pollinator parent, they will provide us with good quality fruits.

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